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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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ACCOMMODATING A TEENAGE ENGLISH LEARNER WITH TOURETTE-RELATED STAMMERING IN UZBEKISTAN STATE MULTILEVEL TEST PREPARATION: A SINGLE-CASE STUDY

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Abstract: The article presents a single-case study of a teenage English learner (Student A) with concurrent stammering, who prepared for the Uzbekistan State Multilevel Test to assess overall English proficiency across all four skills. Before the preparation course started, the student had achieved B1 level (with occasional B2) proficiency in receptive skills; however, in productive skills, he faced difficulties speaking spontaneously within limited time constraints. Drawing on Affective Filter Hypothesis and Language Learning and Study Abroad social interaction framework, several methods were utilized to enhance Student A's productive skills, especially speaking: recorded speaking responses, extended processing time, and digital tools for self-study (COCA and YouGlish). Additionally, authentic listening materials (TED Talks) and official Multilevel Test speaking cue cards were used to improve pronunciation. After 12 weeks, the student's speech length, fluency, and grammatical accuracy increased, word blocks became less frequent, and anxiety was reduced. The article highlights that principled, skill-specific measures can offer implications for state test preparation without lowering assessment standards. However, assessment time limits should be reviewed considering the special needs of all test takers.

Key words: Multilevel test, stammering, Tourette syndrome, affective filter, accommodation, COCA, YouGlish.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada duduqlanish bilan birga kechuvchi nutq buzilishiga ega bo'lgan ingliz tilini o'rganuvchi o'smir (Student A) misolida yagona holat (single-case) tadqiqoti taqdim etiladi. Tadqiqotda ishtirokchi O'zbekiston Davlat Ko'p darajali Testi orqali ingliz tilining to'rtta ko'nikmasi bo'yicha umumiy bilim darajasini baholash uchun tayyorgarlik ko'rgan. Tayyorgarlik kursi boshlanishidan oldin talaba qabul qilish ko'nikmalarida B1 (ba'zan B2) darajasiga ega bo'lgan, biroq ishlab chiqarish (produktiv) ko'nikmalarida, ayniqsa cheklangan vaqt sharoitida erkin nutq ishlab chiqishda qiyinchiliklarga duch kelgan. Affective Filter Hypothesis va Language Learning and Study Abroad ijtimoiy interaktsiya yondashuvi asosida talabaniing produktiv ko'nikmalarini, ayniqsa nutqni rivojlantirish uchun bir qator usullar qo'llanildi: yozib olingan nutq javoblari, qo'shimcha vaqt ajratish va mustaqil ta'lim uchun raqamli vositalar (COCA va YouGlish). Shuningdek, talaffuzni yaxshilash maqsadida autentik tinglab tushunish materiallari (TED Talks) hamda rasmiy Multilevel Test savol kartalaridan foydalanildi. 12 hafta davomida olib borilgan mashg'ulotlardan so'ng talabaniing nutq uzunligi, ravonligi va grammatik aniqligi oshdi, nutqdagi to'xtalishlar kamaydi hamda xavotir darajasi pasaydi. Maqolada ta'kidlanishicha, aniq maqsadga yo'naltirilgan va ko'nikmaga xos metodlar davlat testlariga tayyorgarlik jarayonida baholash standartlarini pasaytirmagan holda samarali natija berishi mumkin. Shu bilan birga, baholashdagi vaqt cheklolarini barcha test topshiruvchilarning maxsus ehtiyojlarini hisobga olgan holda qayta ko'rib chiqish zarur.

Kalit so'zlar: Multilevel test, duduqlanish, Tourette sindromi, affektiv filtr, moslashtirish, COCA, YouGlish.

Аннотация: В статье представлено исследование единичного случая (single-case study) на примере подростка, изучающего английский язык (Student A), с сопутствующим заиканием. Участник готовился к Государственному многоуровневому тесту Узбекистана с целью оценки общего уровня владения английским языком по четырём видам речевой деятельности. До начала подготовительного курса студент обладал уровнем B1 (иногда B2) по рецептивным навыкам, однако в продуктивных навыках, особенно при спонтанной речи в условиях ограниченного времени, испытывал трудности. На основе Affective Filter Hypothesis и Language Learning and Study Abroad были применены методы, направленные на развитие продуктивных навыков, особенно говорения: записанные устные ответы, увеличение времени на обработку информации и цифровые инструменты для самостоятельного обучения (COCA и YouGlish). Дополнительно использовались аутентичные аудиоматериалы (TED Talks) и официальные карточки устной части Multilevel Test для улучшения произношения. По результатам 12-недельного обучения увеличились длина высказывания, беглость и грамматическая точность речи, снизилась частота речевых блоков и уровень тревожности. В статье подчёркивается, что целенаправленные и специфичные по навыкам методы могут быть эффективно применены при подготовке к государственным тестам без снижения стандартов оценивания. Вместе с тем рекомендуется пересмотреть временные ограничения тестирования с учётом особых потребностей всех участников.

Ключевые слова: Multilevel test, заикание, синдром Туретта, аффективный фильтр, адаптация, COCA, YouGlish.

INTRODUCTION

The Uzbekistan State Multilevel Test is a high-stakes test that assesses listening, reading, writing, and speaking skills at proficiency levels from A1 to C1. The speaking part consists of four parts:

Part 1 is divided into:

Part 1.1, where three general, personal questions about everyday topics such as home, family, and hometown are asked, and candidates are given 30 seconds to answer each question; and Part 1.2, where students are first asked to compare two given pictures (Question 1), followed by two additional questions (Questions 2 and 3) regarding the advantages and disadvantages of the ideas presented in the pictures. Each question is allocated 45 seconds.

In Part 2, students need to answer three questions within a given time of 2 minutes. The questions require students to describe different situations from their life experiences.

In Part 3, students are given a statement along with three points supporting and three points opposing it. They need to elaborate on the topic by discussing both sides of the statement and providing their own opinion. The task duration is 2 minutes.

PAPER 4: SPEAKING

The Speaking section consists of **THREE** parts.

PART 1.

- Question 1. Do you like your hometown?
- Question 2. Describe your room.
- Question 3. What do you do on weekends?
- Question 4. What do you see in these pictures?

- Question 5. Do you think it is safer to work in an office?
- Question 6. Would you work in an office or at home?

PART 2.

Describe a time when you faced a disagreement.
How did you handle this problem?
What do you learn from this situation?

PART 3.

All employees should be able to work from home permanently.	
<p>FOR</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working from home helps employees save time and money by avoiding long daily commutes. • Many people feel more comfortable and relaxed at home, which can improve their mood and productivity. • A quiet home environment can help some workers focus better and complete tasks more efficiently. 	<p>AGAINST</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Remote work can make it harder for teams to communicate, share ideas, and build strong working relationships. • Without a clear separation between work and home life, employees may feel more stressed or overworked. • Not all jobs can be done from home, especially those that require special equipment or face-to-face service.

Image source: "Real Multilevel Collection: Multilevel Notion 2025" compiled by Daminjonov Bahtiyor, supervised by Shakhzodakhon Khamroliyeva. Retrieved from the official Telegram channel: t.me/MULTILEVELIIIIII. Accessed on 23.04.2025.

In a multilevel oral exam based on CEFR and IELTS benchmarks, learners' performance is assessed according to four main criteria: fluency and coherence, lexical resource, grammatical range and accuracy, and pronunciation. Fluency refers to the ability of a learner to speak without unnatural hesitation or repetition, whereas coherence denotes the ability to organize thoughts logically and use cohesive devices such as "however" or "furthermore."

LITERATURE REVIEW

Lexical resource refers to an assessment of the variety of vocabulary used, including rare or idiomatically structured expressions where necessary. In terms of grammatical range and accuracy, a learner should demonstrate his/her capacity to produce various sentence structures, ranging from simple to more complex ones, with minimal grammatical mistakes that do not hinder comprehension. As for pronunciation, besides the correct pronunciation of words, it also implies appropriate word stress and sentence intonation. At the B2 level, a learner is expected to produce clear and detailed speech on various topics, demonstrate the ability to express personal opinions supported by arguments, and interact with a certain degree of spontaneity in monologue, which was the most challenging aspect for Student A. For students with speaking disorders such as stammering or Tourette syndrome, the speaking component—with timed parts—can become a source of stress rather than a valid measure of foreign language speaking ability.

As Chapelle (2021) notes, "validity is not regarded as a property or an entity that can be conferred upon a test and accompany it for all future applications and contexts" (p. 4). Instead, validity "pertains to the soundness of specific inferences and applications of test scores to specific groups of people." As such, for a learner who stammers due to Tourette syndrome, it would be invalid to interpret his timed speaking score as indicative of B2-level oral proficiency because the testing situation itself—the countdown timer on the computer screen—would increase the learner's affective filter, causing disfluency.

According to Chapelle (2021), one important inference involved in making a validity argument is the "extrapolation inference," whereby "the test user accepts that the meaning of the score applies to the target context" (p. 5, Table 2.1). However, if the target context is the learner's everyday use of English (in which case the stammerer can ask for additional time or write instead of speaking), then the timed test format would invalidate the extrapolation inference. Krashen's (1985) affective filter hypothesis posits that anxiety, low self-confidence, or lack of motivation raise a mental barrier that prevents comprehensible input from reaching the language acquisition device (p. 4). For a stammering learner, the time pressure of a timed speaking exam risks increasing the affective filter to the point of severe disfluency.

According to Kinginger (2009), social interaction plays a crucial role in improving language skills (p. 422). However, for learners whose spoken language exhibits abnormalities, scaffolding becomes essential. The provision of additional time, recording of responses, and preparation through writing before speaking does not compromise the quality of the test.

The paper describes the preparation process of Student A, an eager and autonomous learner who managed to achieve a solid B1 level of English, with some B2 proficiency in listening and reading, after studying independently for 18 months using Headway Pre-intermediate, Solutions Intermediate, and Grammarway. However, his Tourette syndrome-induced stammering made him reluctant to engage in impromptu discussions. The research question posed is: How should a test preparation teacher facilitate a B1-level stammering student through the Uzbekistan State Multilevel oral exam to obtain a B2-level certificate?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Student Profile. Student A is an autonomous learner and requires little supervision from the teacher. After eighteen months of private classes focused on coursebooks such as Headway Pre-intermediate, Solutions Intermediate, and Grammarway, he managed to reach a B2-level reading competence in some texts, including the ability to make inferences and skim-read. He also achieved B1–B2 levels in listening, demonstrating the ability to understand extended discourse on familiar topics. In writing, he demonstrated a B1 level, marked by coherent paragraphs with occasional mistakes. His speaking was assessed below the B1 level due to his stammering; however, when given time to prepare and the opportunity to record himself before presenting, he reached a B1 level. The cause of Student A's stammering during oral production lies in the symptoms of Tourette syndrome, which include both verbal and motor tics, exacerbated by time pressure and test anxiety.

As Heim, Opitz, and Friederici (2002, as cited in Warren, 2013) illustrate, even simple picture naming involves coordination between various brain regions to retrieve words, process grammar, and produce speech. Given that the student experiences stammering associated with Tourette syndrome, the additional cognitive load under timed test conditions may overwhelm his processing capacity. Anxiety is not merely a secondary emotion; it plays an integral role in both stuttering and vocal tic disorders.

According to Yaruss (2007, in Peltokorpi et al., 2024), speakers with disfluencies “have experienced frustration, shame, and anxiety,” leading them to avoid “difficult words, certain situations, or even speaking altogether.”

This aligns with Krashen’s (1985) affective filter model, where increased anxiety blocks language acquisition, posing a significant challenge for a second-language learner such as Student A during timed examinations.

Lowering the Affective Filter. In accordance with Krashen’s (1985) suggestions, three anxiety-reducing measures were applied over twelve weeks. First, additional time for oral responses was provided throughout the training to encourage automatization, although such accommodations are not permitted during the actual examination. Second, speaking tests were conducted in audio format: Student A recorded his responses individually, without the presence of examiners, and submitted them as audio files via a social media platform. Thus, social anxiety and the resulting stuttering were significantly reduced.

Both types of face, as discussed by Brown and Levinson (1987, as cited in McCabe, 2011, p. 9), are threatened in exam situations: the desire to be liked (positive face) and the desire not to be imposed upon (negative face). In the case of a student with Tourette-induced stammering, the monologic nature of the Multilevel Test speaking component becomes particularly threatening, raising the affective filter (Krashen, 1985) to the extent that disfluency increases and communicative competence is inhibited.

As McCabe (2011) states, in conversation people may use discourse markers such as well to “soften the impact of what is being said, so that the speaker does not sound too definite or certain” (p. 12). For Student A, the use of such markers was not indicative of weakness but rather a pragmatic strategy, which became feasible only after removing the pressure of real-time, timed responses. Third, a writing-first approach was implemented, whereby Student A wrote bullet points for each speaking task without time constraints before delivering responses.

According to Taylor (2013), “discourse analysis refers to the close examination of language and language use as evidence for features of society and social life” (p. 4). In this study, Student A’s disfluencies are interpreted not only as linguistic inaccuracies but also as indicators of an elevated affective filter under exam conditions. Taylor further emphasizes that language is “inextricably linked to its social context” (p. 2); therefore, the intervention aimed to reshape the social context of assessment through recordings, extended time, and a writing-first approach.

Digital Tools for Accuracy and Fluency. Two digital tools were employed to enhance accuracy and fluency. First, the Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA) was recommended to Student A for verifying collocations, such as distinguishing “make a decision” from “do a decision.”

According to Green (2018, p. 3), “corpus-based pedagogy aids students in understanding and analyzing subtle differences in language structure and enables them to inductively derive usage rules.” Student A used COCA autonomously prior to recording his monologues, which reduced anxiety related to self-monitoring by allowing pre-verification of language use.

Green (2018, p. 6) further notes that in learner-centered approaches, students are encouraged to independently resolve questions regarding form, meaning, and use, while the teacher facilitates guided autonomy. Second, YouGlish was used to improve pronunciation and prosody. Student A listened to several examples of target phrases (e.g., “on the other hand,” “from my perspective”) and practiced shadowing. This process helped develop motor patterns conducive to fluent speech production without stuttering.

Materials for Authentic Test Preparation. Authentic speaking tasks from previous examinations were used for practice. AI-based tools such as DeepSeek, ChatGPT, and Gemini were utilized to generate complex responses incorporating C1–C2 level discourse markers, thereby increasing the likelihood of achieving higher scores. Additionally, short TED Talks (approximately three minutes) were selected for listening practice, as they provide authentic and engaging input beyond textbook language. These materials support the development of key listening skills, such as identifying main ideas and specific details, thereby enhancing overall comprehension. As noted by Student A, the use of authentic materials increased engagement and reduced anxiety related to unfamiliar or deceptive test items.

Lesson Sequence. A standard 90-minute lesson consisted of several structured stages aimed at reducing anxiety and gradually developing communicative competence. The initial stage involved a ten-minute warm-up, during which students wrote three sentences expressing agreement or disagreement with a debate topic (e.g., “Social media has more disadvantages than advantages”). The second stage, lasting twenty minutes, focused on listening: students watched a TED Talk on the same topic while Student A took notes on key arguments without speaking. In the third stage (twenty minutes), Student A conducted a COCA search for collocations (e.g., “mitigate the risk,” “a compelling argument”) and practiced pronunciation using YouGlish. The fourth stage involved writing a structured outline for Multilevel Part 3 within twenty minutes. Finally, in the last stage, Student A recorded a two-minute response for the speaking test (Part 3) and conducted self-assessment using a checklist covering fluency, range, accuracy, and task achievement.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

At the end of the twelve-week intervention period, Student A exhibited notable improvements in his test results in terms of recorded Multilevel Test speaking assessments. He demonstrated an increase in the duration of monologues to 20-30 seconds or more in all parts of the speaking test. The number of word blocks per minute decreased from twelve to fifteen at baseline to four to six per minute at the end of the intervention period. In terms of collocation usage based on COCA, his number of collocations per monologue increased from one or two in the baseline phase to three or four after twelve weeks. Most significantly, his anxiety levels, measured on a scale of one to ten, decreased from eight out of ten in the initial phase to three out of ten when making a self-recording in the final twelve-week phase. Collocations such as “reach a compromise” and “present a counterargument” were utilized effectively by Student A during the recording of his monologues. According to him, the process of listening to authentic TED Talks made him more focused on his task and helped him feel less anxious about encountering unfamiliar questions in tests. It is worth noting that his independent learning approach benefited him during this intervention period, as he utilized YouGlish and COCA on his own and also made self-recordings between lessons. The findings show that low-anxiety conditions work effectively for students with Tourette syndrome-related stammering when preparing for speaking examinations. This is because the number of word blocks in their speech decreased from twelve to fifteen per minute to four to six per minute, implying that through recorded speaking tasks, their affective filter decreased to an extent that their B2-level knowledge could be demonstrated without impediment. The increased use of collocations by the student, from zero or one to three or four per monologue, shows that computer software such as COCA can be incorporated into test preparation even for intermediate-level students.

Nonetheless, the main drawback of this technique is the limited response time in computer-based speaking tasks. Currently, the Uzbekistan State Multilevel Test does not provide students with speech disorders unlimited time. Student A ultimately took the exam under time-constrained conditions, with a ticking clock on the screen. Nevertheless, he scored 52 out of 64 (B2 level; overall C1 level score is 75) on the speaking test, which corresponds to a low B2 level, and achieved an overall score of 56 across four skills, which is an average B2. This result enables him to apply to high-stakes state universities in Uzbekistan with a full score in the foreign language component where required. This conclusion may serve as a useful insight for teachers of speaking courses in terms of exam preparation. Several pedagogical implications can be outlined regarding test preparation classes in Uzbekistan. First, the importance of diagnostic differentiation must be recognized: not all stammering cases are equal; thus, teachers must determine whether a learner’s difficulties result from excessive nervousness, motor-planning issues, or a combination of both. Second, low-risk recording tasks can be incorporated into homework because allowing B1 students to record speech activities can minimize affective filters without eliminating live practice. Third, tools such as COCA and YouGlish are readily available and free of charge; moreover, they demonstrate native-like usage, which intermediate learners often perceive as inaccessible. Finally, the issue should be addressed at the level of advocacy: at present, the Multilevel Test does not offer accommodations for neurodivergent learners, but the results of this case study may serve as a basis for future changes. Nevertheless, the current study represents only a single-case design, and further research is required to confirm its generalizability. Future research may explore similar accommodations for learners with dyslexia and ADHD taking the Uzbekistan State Multilevel Test, the impact of recording on timed live speech, and existing official accommodation policies for high-stakes testing in Central Asia.

According to Tomlinson (2001), differentiation does not mean lowering standards but providing “different avenues to acquiring content, to processing or making sense of ideas, and to developing products so that each student can learn effectively” (p. 1). This approach was applied in the current experiment by giving Student A more time to practice speaking skills, allowing him to write bullet points before recording, and permitting submission of an audio file rather than requiring live performance. Tomlinson further notes that “many students can show what they know far better in a product than on a written test” (p. 21). In this case, Student A demonstrated B2-level proficiency in monologues but was unable to demonstrate it during live performance. Such adjustments do not affect the quality of evaluation, as the results reflect the intended construct (English language speaking skills) rather than the symptoms of Tourette syndrome.

CONCLUSION

Preparing a learner with Tourette-related stammering for the Uzbekistan State Multilevel Test requires moving beyond generic speaking practice toward a principled, theoretically grounded approach. By reducing the affective filter as described by Krashen (1985), scaffolding social interaction as advocated by Kinginger (2009), and integrating freely available digital tools such as COCA and YouGlish, teachers can help neurodivergent students demonstrate their true B2 ability. Student A’s case shows that, with recorded assessments,

authentic materials, including TED Talks and real Multilevel Test cue cards, and explicit strategy instruction, even a high-anxiety speaker can succeed.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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